

A short insight into 5G

Tahreem Fatima, member IEEE org.

What is 5G?

Mobile broadband

5G technology is interpreted in terms of extreme broadband with eMBB-peak >10Gbps as compared to 4G with peak of 1 Gbp. This is to give user an experience of unlimited eMBB of 100 Mbps whenever needed with 5G and a 10-100Mbps with 4G technology.

Reliability and latency

5G is a prequel of 4G with machine communication of ultra low latency of upto 1ms and slicing at a micro level and Reliability of 3-6*9. With 4G latency is upto 10 ms and reliability is 3-5*9.

IEEE 802.11 technologies can be used to support several advanced use cases, including 5G IMT-2020

IMT-2020 use cases

- enhanced Mobile BroadBand: Indoor Hotspot and Dense Urban and
- Internet of Things -> massive Machine Type Communications
- Low Latency -> Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications

802.11ay use cases range from ultra-short range/high throughput kiosk to fixed wireless access to wireless backhaul

20Gbps+ rates are defined
License- Exempt bands above 45Gbps
Completion in 2020; First chipsets announced

802.11ay Use Cases:

- Ultra-Short Range
- 8K UHD - Smart Home
- AR/VR and wearables
- Data Center Inter Rack connectivity
- Video / Mass-Data distribution
- Mobile Offloading and MBO
- Mobile Fronthauling
- Wireless Backhauling (w. multi-hop)
- Office Docking
- Fixed Wireless Access

5G Applications

5G Use Cases:

- Fixed Wireless Access
- Wireless backhauling (with multi-hop)
- Very High Throughput Short Range

Massive Connectivity

IOT and advanced sensors

With 4G eMTC and NB-IOT is 100,000 devices per km square and 5-10 years on battery.

With 5G mTC is for everything with >10years on battery. With mobile connectivity of 1000,000 devices per km square with inclusion of IOT and sensors.

Differentiating 5G Technologies

5G Spectrum

5G spectrum is given in the figure above. What are the health implications of such an extended spectrum of 5G is at large unknown and with comparison of previous 4G and even 3G studies, there have been studies with serious health implications whether ignored or seldomly taken into account by mass telecommunication services. To point out here such a dose of radio waves with 60GHz to 100GHz has never been encountered not at this scale before.

With extreme importance of genetic material of all life forms on earth and its intricate reliance on electromagnetic forces, the effect of ionising and other radiations like radio waves, the consequences of such revolutions is yet to come with extreme impact even though in the presence of alternate resources like fibre optic technologies with much lesser side effects.

The proposed benefits of 5G are often advocated as

The drivers for 5G

Manufacturing
Dynamic production control, capacity and agility

Sports & Entertainment
Immersive device AR, with personalized experience

Power Industry
Drones to inspect, identify proactively address issues

Transportation
Dynamic platooning with shorter distances

Public Safety
Instantaneous, proactive threat recognition via video

Health Care
Remotely supported complex health interventions

Mining
Autonomous robotic machinery

And taken into account the general public has much lesser implications than the military and technical data control centres. Having said that the face of warfare is yet to change entirely based on this and alike technologies.

5G Architecture

Clearly given in the figure above, the 5G deployment options, with modifications in 4G in both user and control plane.

5G Spectrum

With 5G spectrum cell analysts comparison is clearly seen in the picture above.

Given the requirement of cellular analysis without stating the purpose is albeit keeping the subject in shade.

Wherever other potential technologies can thrive to the acquired level, usage and implications of 5G are ought to be considered more seriously.

MIMO and 3D-Beamforming principles

Differentiating 5G Technologies

Massive Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) and 3D-Beamforming principles

Differentiating 5G Technologies

Massive Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) and 3D-Beamforming principles

5G multi connectivity

Differentiating 5G Technologies

5G Access and Multi-connectivity

5G core Principles

Differentiating 5G Technologies

5G Core principles

Network Slicing

Differentiating 5G Technologies

Network Slicing – for various use cases and requirements

Differentiating 5G Technologies

Network Slicing principle

Differentiating 5G Technologies

Network Slicing End to End Orchestration

End-to-End (E2E) Network Slice Orchestration

- E2E Service Orchestration / onboarding
- E2E Monitoring and management

Offload traffic from mobile devices-future trends

Offload Traffic from Mobile Devices on to Wi-Fi is Significant and Increasing

Source of charts: Cisco VNI 2019

Offload Traffic from Mobile Devices on to Wi-Fi is Significant and Increasing

Source of charts: Cisco VNI 2019

Wi-Fi in 5G

Foundations for Wi-Fi in 5G Rel-15: Technology Agnostic Interface

- 3GPP 5G specifications integrate support for non-3GPP access networks

Consumer role in trend settings

Indoor Hotspot: Wi-Fi today can meet the needs of indoor and outdoor hotspots: for a single home user or a whole stadium of users

2020: [Wi-Fi Usage Surges at Super Bowl LIV For Seventh Year in a Row with 26TB of data](#)

2019: [Super Bowl 53 smashes Wi-Fi record with 24 TB of traffic at Mercedes-Benz Stadium](#)

Average Wi-Fi data use per connected fan also set a new record, with the per-fan mark of 492.3 megabytes per user eclipsing [last year's mark](#) of 407.4.

2018: a huge leap from the official [16.31 TB](#) seen at 2018 Super Bowl 52 in Minneapolis at U.S. Bank Stadium

Source: <https://investor.extremenetworks.com/news-releases/news-release-details/wi-fi-usage-surges-super-bowl-liv-seventh-year-row>
<https://www.extremenetworks.com/resources/slideshare/wi-fi-engagements-from-super-bowl-liv/>

mmWave Frequency for 5G

60 GHz Fixed Wireless Use Case

"The 14 GHz of contiguous spectrum in the band offers more bandwidth than any other licensed or unlicensed mmWave band. Further, the 60 GHz band has chipsets and technology currently available on the commercial market."

"In the U.S., unlicensed mmWave frequencies available for 5G primarily cover the band from 57 – 71 GHz, called the V-Band, or 60 GHz band. This band offers 14 GHz of contiguous spectrum, which is more than all other licensed and unlicensed bands combined. **This makes the 60 GHz band an excellent alternative to licensed mmWave frequencies for smaller providers, as it can be used to deliver 5G performance for the minimal cost of available 60 GHz infrastructure products.**

<https://go.siklu.com/hubfs/Content/White%20Papers/Maravedis%20Industry%20Overview:%205G%20Fixed%20Wireless%20Gigabit%20Services%20Today.pdf>

<https://www.fiercewireless.com/wireless/60-ghz-band-particularly-appealing-for-fixed-wireless-report>

Technology behind 5G

IEEE 802.11 defined technologies provide radio technology components to meet the 5G Use cases and the comprehensive 5G service vision

- IEEE 802.11 components are now and will be an important part of carrier deployments continuing into the future
- IEEE 802.11ax technologies including OFDMA and MU-MIMO support the requirements of 5G use cases including
 - Indoor Hotspot
 - Dense Urban
- IEEE 802.11ay very high throughput 60GHz defined operation including MIMO and channel aggregation supports
 - High throughput and
 - Fixed wireless use cases

Summary conclusion

Understanding 5G Fundamentals (duration in minutes)

5G System Overview

The Need for 5G	12
5G potential use cases	8
5G System requirements	23
Time line for 5G standards and roll-out	8
The Need for a new architecture	7
5G Network deployment options	9
3GPP 5G system architecture	11
Service Based Architecture	14

5G Core Network Principles

5G Core Network Functions	11
5G System Procedures	25
5G Network Slicing overview	9
5G Network architecture for Network Slicing	7
5G Network Slicing operation	5
5G Radio Access Network Slicing	7
5G System QoS	11
5G System Security	6
Verticals and Specific services support	10

5G New Radio Principles

5G NR-RAN Architecture	14
5G NR-RAN Protocols	20
Multiple access	5
5G NR Spectrum	19
Bandwidth part operation	4
Massive MIMO and Beamforming principle	15
Beam Management	9
Multi-RAT Dual Connectivity	14

IEEE 802.11 Radio Standards

IEEE 802.11 Radio Standards Evolution	10
IEEE 802.11 Radio Technology Components (with Focus on 802.11ax, 11ad, 11ay)	20
IEEE 802.11 Use Cases for 5G: Fixed Wireless Access, Backhaul, VHT/Line of Sight, Dense Urban and Indoor Hotspot	30